

METHODS ON HOW TO IMPROVE TEACHING READING

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Annotation: As is known, the activity in the assimilation of information in schoolchildren occurs on the basis of their own views and interests, which is the main means of motivating educational activities. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the personal individualization of students, correlate speech actions with their real feelings, thoughts and interests.

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As lexical units accumulate, many schoolchildren need visual support because it is extremely difficult to perceive speech only by ear. This is especially true for those schoolchildren whose visual memory is better developed than auditory memory. That's why reading is so important.

Reading is one of the most important types of communicative and cognitive activity for students. This activity is aimed at extracting information from a written fixed text. Reading performs various functions: it serves for practical mastery of a foreign language, is a means of learning a language and culture, a means of information and educational activities and a means of self-education. As you know, reading contributes to the development of other types of communicative activity. It is reading that gives the greatest opportunities for the education and comprehensive development of schoolchildren by means of a foreign language.

When teaching reading at the initial stage, it is important to teach the student to read correctly, that is, to teach him to voice graphemes, and extract thoughts, that is, to understand, evaluate, and use the information of the text. These skills depend on how fast the child reads. By reading technique we mean not only the fast and accurate correlation of sound and letter, but also the correlation of the sound-letter bundle with the semantic meaning of what the child is reading. It is the high level of mastery of the reading technique that allows you to achieve the result of the reading process itself – fast and high-quality information extraction. However, this is not possible if the student does not have enough language skills, does not know how or reproduces sounds incorrectly.

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Every century comes up with its own methods of teaching reading. Then he forgets them, in order to "rediscover" them a few decades later and admire them anew. Everyone has their own charm. However, let's look at all this diversity. There are two main, fundamentally opposite methods of teaching reading. One is called the whole word method, the other is phonological. For a long time, there were discussions on whether phonetics should be taught at all. By 1930, a number of studies had been conducted on this topic, and everyone came to the conclusion that phonetics was necessary, the only question was how and to what extent to give it to schoolchildren. For example, such an experiment was set up. A group of schoolchildren aged five to six years was divided in half, with the first subgroup being taught to read by the method of whole words, the second by the phonological method. When the schoolchildren started reading, they were tested. At the first stage, the schoolchildren from the first group read aloud and to themselves better. "Phonological" schoolchildren coped more easily with unfamiliar words and by the end of the second grade surpassed their classmates in terms of perception and richness of vocabulary. According to the observations of scientists, "pedigreed" schoolchildren made typical mistakes. For example, reading the caption under the picture, they replaced words that were close in meaning. Instead of "tiger" they could say "lion", instead of "girl" - "schoolchildren", instead of "car" - "wheels". The desire

to fix the word for a strictly defined meaning led to the fact that during the whole year of study these schoolchildren could not learn to read new words without anyone's help. In fairness, it should be said that "phonological" schoolchildren had difficulty reading those words where the letters were rearranged or replaced with similar ones. Thus, it became clear that phonetics is necessary for most small readers. Recent studies have confirmed that people spell words. But due to the fact that this process happens instantly, it seems that we perceive the whole word.

Going further in research, psychologists realized that reading is saying a text to yourself. Proponents of the theory of perception of the text as a whole believed and believe that we perceive words from the text directly. But experiments have shown that while reading to yourself, the same part of the brain is involved as when reading aloud. So, in order to read freely, it is necessary to easily and quickly recognize letters and correlate them with sounds. And the simplest cramming of phonetics turns out to be much more effective than other tricks and techniques.

Oddly enough, you can learn to read without knowing the alphabet. Followers of the "whole words" method urge not to teach the child letters. And only recently have the final conclusions of scientists become known: only knowledge of letters makes the process of learning to read as successful as possible. An experiment was conducted. Schoolchildren were shown cards with words. Only in one group these words were captions under pictures, and in the other the same words were given without illustration. Each group was presented with the same four words. Then the schoolchildren were connected, the cards were shuffled and shown again. It turned out that children learn words only on the cards they studied on. That is, a child who remembers words with an illustration is much less likely to recognize the graphic appearance of the word than someone who memorized the spelling in its "pure form".

This indirectly confirms the fact that the alphabet is necessary. But the main thing is not how the letters are called, but what they mean. Schoolchildren should not so much know the names and sequence of letters as learn to pay attention to the letters, perceive them as part of the whole. In addition, the alphabet is an abstract code. A kid who has dealt with real things before begins to use symbols, and this is the first step to the development of abstract thinking. There cannot be one universal method of teaching reading in any language. But the general approach can be: to start learning with an understanding of letters and sounds, with phonetics. This principle works in almost any language. Even in China, where hieroglyphs are traditionally used in writing, for the last 50 years children have been taught to read words using the Latin alphabet first, and then they switch to the traditional spelling. In some languages, the relationship between letters and phonemes is very, very complicated. For example, in English, many words are read completely differently than they are written. The rules of reading depend on whether the syllable is closed or open, on the

order of letters and on their combinations with each other. Some sounds can affect the pronunciation of others and so on. That is why the alphabet for James Pitman's initial reading instruction and the whole-language method (perception of the text as a whole) used to be very popular in English. Today, in America, at the state level, a project is being considered for the mandatory introduction of phonetics into the curriculum in all states. A few decades ago, the method was the same: first, schoolchildren learned the names of letters, then sounds, and then connected letters into syllables. The difficulty was that first graders could not learn the difference between how a letter is called and how it is pronounced for a long time. The syllables turned out to be long, and it was very difficult for the child to keep several letters in his head. In recent years, the principle of warehouses - phonemes has been successfully used. So, we found out that a child needs to know phonetics. But this does not mean that the kid should memorize boring rules and distinguish qualitative reduction from quantitative. The main thing that needs to be maintained is an interest in studying. And there is one rule here: the child is interested as long as his capabilities coincide with the tasks set.

It is necessary to make sure that the child succeeds so that his successes are obvious. For example, take for mastering a couple of dozen words denoting objects in the house. If you hang signs with words on these objects, the baby will soon begin to recognize familiar inscriptions. Then you can play a guessing game, a lotto game with the same words - and the child will feel confident in his abilities.

Only against the background of positive emotions will further training be effective. But it is not a sin to prepare the youngest schoolchildren for learning to read in the future. The recipe here is simple: read aloud to them as much as possible. Moreover, the texts should exceed the language level of the child in their vocabulary. In addition, correct reading, according to experts, involves pauses, unfinished thoughts, complex questions that require reflection. One-and-a-half-year-old schoolchildren, whose parents read books in this way, outstripped their peers in development by eight months!

So, despite the ongoing debate about how to teach reading, a mandatory element has been defined that does not depend on a particular language: mastering the correspondences between letters and sounds. This step is the first, but not the last on the way to a deep and complete mastery of native speech.

Reference:

1. Hewings, A. and Hewings, M. Grammar and Context, London, Routledge, 2004

2. Wells, W. H. G. 'An experimental approach to the interpretation of focus in spoken English' in Johns-Lewis, C. (ed.) *Intonation in Discourse*, London, Croom Helm. 1986

3. Kama Einhorn. *ESL Activities and Mini-Books for Every Classroom*. Scholastic Publishing. New York. 2011

